

Number of Thermal Time Constants - nTTC

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Abstract

Thermal Time Constant (TTC) indicates the time required for change of 63.2% of temperature difference.

This work develops useful application of TTC for determination of temperature change in buildings.

Higher TTC results in slower change of room temperature, contributing to thermal comfort, to quality of the building and to energy conservation. The procedure developed in the work is for both purposes: to find the temperature change in the period of time and to find the period of time of specific temperature change.

Thermal Time Constant – TTC

The term "Thermal Time Constant – TTC" in relation to building element is clearly described in publication [1].

Thermal Time Constant (TTC) is a measurement of the time required for a building element to change 63.2% of the difference between its initial and final body temperature when subjected to a step function change in temperature, under zero power conditions.

The unit of TTC is hour (TTC is expressed in hours).

TTC may be determined using publication [2].

The publication [1] includes a formula for "Time Constant Value", the above mentioned 63.2%.

Formula 1 – Time Constant Value

$$1 - 1/e = 0.632$$

e - Euler's Number, approximately 2.7182818284590452353602874713527

Euler's Number can be generated in MS-Excel applying the following formula:

Formula 2 – Calculation of Euler Number in MS-Excel

$$=EXP(1)$$

Formula 3 – Determination of Time Constant Value in MS-Excel

$$=1-1/EXP(1)$$

Calculation of Time Constant Value using MS-Excel results in 0.632120558828558.

The publication [1] includes also an example demonstrating the use of Thermal Time Constant.

In the example the building's TTC is 40 hours. The room temperature of the building was kept as 18°C for long time. At the starting point, all internal and external energy sources were switched off, while the ambient temperature is 8°C. For the purpose of this example, the ambient temperature remains constant day and night 8°C and there is no solar radiation. The room temperature in the building will gradually decrease. This is not linear process. Theoretically, the room temperature will reach 8°C at endless time (never), but will get close to it slower and slower. The initial difference between 18°C room temperature of the building and 8°C ambient temperature is 10°C.

Formula 4 – Initial temperature difference

$$\Delta T_0 = T_{in0} - T_{out}$$

$$\Delta T_0 = 18^{\circ}\text{C} - 8^{\circ}\text{C} = 10^{\circ}\text{C}$$

ΔT_0 Initial temperature difference, °C
 $T_{in0} = 18^{\circ}\text{C}$ Initial room temperature, °C
 $T_{out} = 8^{\circ}\text{C}$ Ambient temperature, °C

The TTC of the example is 40 hours. TTC of 40 hours means that the initial temperature difference will be decreased by the Time Constant Value (63.2%) in 40 hours.

Formula 5 – Temperature difference after one TTC

$$\Delta T_{1TTC} = \Delta T_0 * (1 - (1 - 1/e))$$

ΔT_{1TTC} Temperature difference after one TTC, °C
 $1 - 1/e$ Time Constant Value = 63.2%

$$\Delta T_{1TTC} = \Delta T_0 * 1/e$$

In the example case:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta T_{1TTC} &= 10^{\circ}\text{C} * 1/2.718 \\ &= 3.68^{\circ}\text{C} \end{aligned}$$

The temperature difference was reduced by 6.32°C, which means that the new temperature difference (after 40 hours) is 3.68°C and the new room temperature (after 40 hours) is 8°C + 3.68°C = 11.68°C

Formula 6 - New room temperature after one TTC

$$T_{in1TTC} = T_{out} + \Delta T_0 * (1/e)$$

$$T_{in1TTC} = 8 + 10 / 2.718 = 11.68^{\circ}\text{C}$$

T_{in1TTC} New room temperature after one TTC, °C
e Euler Number

Two Thermal Time Constants

The above analysis was related to one TTC for example of TTC=40 hr.

This section includes considerations related to 2 TTCs, 2 x 40 hr = 80hr.

In the first TTC the temperature difference was reduced by Time Constant Value (63.2%).

During the second TTC, the new temperature difference will be reduced again by the Time Constant Value (63.2%).

Formula 7 – Temperature difference after two TTCs

$$\Delta T_{2TTC} = \Delta T_{1TTC} * (1 - (1 - 1/e))$$

$$\Delta T_{2TTC} = \Delta T_{1TTC} * (1/e)$$

$$\Delta T_{1TTC} = \Delta T_0 * (1/e)$$

$$\Delta T_{2TTC} = \Delta T_0 * (1/e) * (1/e)$$

$$\Delta T_{2TTC} = \Delta T_0 * (1/e)^2$$

$$\Delta T_{2TTC} = \Delta T_0 / (e^2)$$

ΔT_{2TTC} Temperature difference after two TTCs, °C
1 - 1/e Time Constant Value = 63.2%

In the example case:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta T_{2TTC} &= 10^{\circ}\text{C} * (1 / 2.718)^2 \\ &= 1.35^{\circ}\text{C} \end{aligned}$$

The temperature difference was reduced by 63.2% during the first TTC reaching the 3.68°C value. This new temperature difference was further reduced during the second TTC period by additional 63.2% reaching 1.35°C value.

The new temperature difference after two TTCs (40 hours and additional 40 hours) is 1.35°C and the new room temperature (after 80 hours) is 8°C + 1.35°C = 9.35°C

Formula 8 - New room temperature after two TTCs

$$\mathbf{T_{in2TTC}} = T_{out} + \mathbf{\Delta T_{1TTC}} * (1 - (1 - 1/e))$$

$$\mathbf{T_{in2TTC}} = T_{out} + \mathbf{\Delta T_{1TTC}} * 1/e$$

$$\mathbf{T_{in2TTC}} = T_{out} + (\Delta T_0 * 1/e) * 1/e$$

$$\mathbf{T_{in2TTC}} = T_{out} + \Delta T_0 * (1/e)^2$$

$$\mathbf{T_{in2TTC}} = T_{out} + \Delta T_0 / (e^2)$$

T_{in2TTC} New room temperature after two TTCs, °C

In the example case:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{T_{in2TTC}} &= 8 + 10 / (2.718^2) \\ &= 9.35^\circ\text{C} \end{aligned}$$

Number of Thermal Time Constants

The above procedure can be repeated for any number, based on general formula:

Formula 9 – Temperature difference after n TTCs

$$\Delta T_{nTTC} = \Delta T_0 / (e^n)$$

n number of TTCs
 ΔT_{nTTC} temperature difference after n TTCs

Considering 7 TTCs, which is 7 x 40 hours = 280hr in the example case:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta T_{7TTC} &= 10 / (e^7) \\ &= 0.009^\circ\text{C} \end{aligned}$$

Formula 10 - New room temperature after n TTCs

$$T_{innTTC} = T_{out} + \Delta T_0 / (e^n)$$

n number of TTCs
 T_{innTTC} New room temperature after n TTCs, °C

Considering 7 TTCs, which is 7 x 40 hours = 280hr in the example case:

$$\begin{aligned} T_{in7TTC} &= 8 + 10 / (e^7) \\ &= 8.009^\circ\text{C} \end{aligned}$$

Fraction of Thermal Time Constant

The above formulas may be used also for fraction of Thermal Time Constants. Considering 15% of TTC, which is 40 hours * 15% = 6hr, in the example case:

$$\Delta T_{nTTC} = \Delta T_0 / (e^n)$$

$$n = 15\%$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta T_{15\%TTC} &= 10 / (e^{0.15}) \\ &= 8.61^\circ\text{C} \end{aligned}$$

$$T_{in nTTC} = T_{out} + \Delta T_0 / (e^n)$$

$$n = 15\%$$

$$\begin{aligned} T_{in 15\%TTC} &= 8 + 10 / (e^{0.15}) \\ &= 16.61^\circ\text{C} \end{aligned}$$

The meaning of the above example for building having 40hr TTC is that after 15% of TTC, which is 6 hours, the room temperature will drop from 18°C to 16.61°C.

Room Temperature Calculations Based on TTC

The above formulas allow calculations of period of time required for specific room temperature change.

The formula for temperature difference depends on number of TTCs:

$$\Delta T_{nTTC} = \Delta T_0 / (e^n)$$

The question is which value of n should be applied to receive ΔT of 1°C.

The above formula should be displayed in the following form to find the number of TTCs:

$$y = b^n$$

This allows determination of "n" using logarithm:

$$n = \log(b,y)$$

The above formula may be displayed in the required form as follows:

$$\Delta T_{nTTC} = \Delta T_0 / (e^n)$$

$$(e^n) = \Delta T_0 / \Delta T_{nTTC}$$

$$y = \Delta T_0 / \Delta T_{nTTC}$$

$$y = e^n$$

$$n = \log(e,y)$$

Formula 11 – Number of TTCs to reach specified room temperature

$$n = \ln(y)$$

$$y = \Delta T_0 / \Delta T_{nTTC}$$

$$\Delta T_{nTTC} = T_{in} - T_{out}$$

n number of TTCs

ΔT_0 initial difference between room temperature and ambient temperature, °C, in the example case = 10°C

T_{in} specified room temperature for which the number of TTCs is calculated, °C

T_{out} ambient temperature, °C, in the example case = 8°C

Table 1 – Time required for room temperature change for TTC=40hr

Room Temp	Temp Drop	y			No of TTCs	Time to reach
Tin	Tin0 - Tin	$\Delta TnTTC$	$\Delta TnTTC / \Delta T0$	$\Delta T0 / \Delta TnTTC$	n	hr
18	0	10	1	1.00	0.00	0.00
17	1	9	0.9	1.11	0.11	4.21
16	2	8	0.8	1.25	0.22	8.93
15	3	7	0.7	1.43	0.36	14.27
14	4	6	0.6	1.67	0.51	20.43
13	5	5	0.5	2.00	0.69	27.73
12	6	4	0.4	2.50	0.92	36.65
11	7	3	0.3	3.33	1.20	48.16
10	8	2	0.2	5.00	1.61	64.38
9	9	1	0.1	10.00	2.30	92.10
8.5	9.5	0.5	0.05	20.00	3.00	119.83

The temperature drop of the first 1°C, from 18°C to 17°C, is relatively fast and takes 0.11 TTC. In case of the example, the building TTC is 40 hours, it means that the temperature drop from 18°C to 17°C will take 4.21 hours.

The temperature drop of the next degree will take already more time.

Temperature drop from 18°C to 9°C, which is 90% of the initial temperature difference between the room temperature and the ambient temperature, will take already 2.3 TTC, more then 90 hours.

TTC as part of Energy Rating of Buildings system

As demonstrated on the above example, TTC allows easy determination of room temperature change of the building, indicating temperature comfort. In the above example, the temperature drop from comfortable 18°C to not comfortable 17°C, will take about 4 hours for TTC = 40hr, about 2 hours for TTC = 20hr and 11 hours for TTC = 100hr.

Similarly, the temperature increase in hot summer from comfortable 26°C to not comfortable 27°C will take the same time periods as calculated above, considering 36°C hot ambient temperature.

TTC is very useful and very important information for the home tenant. Higher TTC results in slower change of room temperature, contributing to thermal comfort, to quality of the building and to energy conservation.

That's why the TTC parameter should be included in energy rating of buildings system, building energy labeling system and green buildings standards.

References

1. Thermal Time Constant – TTC, Joseph Nowarski, DOI:10.5281/zenodo.6530723
2. Energy and Thermal Time Constant in Buildings – TTC, Joseph Nowarski, ASIN:B01F18XGQK

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